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The Impact of Supply Chain Integration on Performance in Vietnamese Seafood Enterprises: Proposing a Research Model

Author Details: Thi Song Lam Tran
General Department of Defense Industry

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review previous studies on supply chain integration and the impact of supply chain integration on business performance of Vietnamese seafood enterprises. The study has proposed future research model.

Keywords: *Supply chain integration, performance.*

1. Introduction

With a coastline of more than 3,200 km, Vietnam has a maritime exclusive economic zone of more than 1 million square kilometers. Vietnam also has a large inland water area of more than 1.4 million hectares thanks to a dense system of rivers and lagoons. The geographical location and favorable natural conditions help Vietnam have many outstanding strengths to develop the seafood industry. For a long time, Vietnam has become the leading seafood producer and exporter in the region, along with Indonesia and Thailand. Seafood export becomes one of the important sectors of the economy.

Vietnam has a dense system of rivers and a long sea route, which is very convenient for developing fishing and aquaculture activities. Vietnam's seafood output has maintained a continuous growth over the past 17 years with an average increase of 9.07% per year. With the government's policy of promoting development, aquaculture activities have made strong progress, production has continuously increased in recent years, reaching an average of 12.77% per year, making a significant contribution to the growth of the country's total seafood production.

According to the report of the Directorate of Fisheries, the growth rate of seafood production in 2020 will continue to maintain. The growth rate of seafood production value (2010 constant price) reached 3.05% compared to 2019, the total output reached 8.4 million tons, an increase of 1.8% (of which, the fishing output reached 8.4 million tons). 3.85 million tons, up 2.1%, aquaculture 4.56 million tons, up 1.5%). Export turnover is estimated at 8.4 billion USD.

Recent scientific and technological advances of communication and transportation lead to globalization. Due to the needs and requirements of customers globalization has been changed and developed. Customers need the right product at the right place, at the right time, with high quality and the right cost. Any organization that wants to compete in the recent market must match the customer requirements mentioned above. To meet customer requirements, organizations should improve all their operations and processes. Supply chain management is a system that improves all activities performed by the organization. Supply chain management is a complex system that includes all support activities from suppliers to after-sales services. To be able to grow and survive, any organization must identify its strengths and weaknesses, promote strengths and overcome weaknesses. Implementing supply chain management can be a source of competitive advantage leading to better overall organizational performance.

Vaidya and Hudnurkar (2012) state that supply chain collaboration plays an important role in improving organizational performance and gaining competitive advantage. Cooper et al. (1997) states that in order to

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utilize the supply chain to its fullest potential, organizations must integrate their goals. Vaidya et al. (2012) mentioned that supply chain partners need to integrate different factors to ensure competitive advantage, increase profit margins and financial cooperation to ensure product design. creative products. Lambert et al. (2000) argue that supply chain management requires integration and coordination to respond to changes in consumer demand. Finally, Frohlich and Westbrook, (2001) have shown that supply chain integration positively affects firm performance.

2. Research overview on the impact of supply chain integration on performance

Xu et al (2014) explored the mediating impact of supply chain integration (Suppliers and customers) on enterprise business. Huo Model (2012): Considered the impact of supply chain integration (internal, customer and supplier integration) on company performance (customer-oriented, supplier-oriented) level and financial performance). Zelbst et al (2009) examined the impact of supply chain linkages (strength, benefits, and risk reduction) on supply chain performance. Rosenzweig et al. (2002) studied the impact of supply chain integration intensity on both competitive priorities (product quality, process flexibility, cost leadership, and delivery reliability) and business performance (return on investment, revenue from new products, customer satisfaction and sales growth). Some specific studies are as follows:

1. Rosenzweig et al. (2002) study titled: "Impact of integrated strategy on competitiveness and business performance: An exploratory study of consumer product manufacturers", aiming to see examine the intensity of supply chain integration on business operations. The study surveyed in 1997 from a target audience that included manufacturers in the top sales groups in 35 countries. Units of analysis are broad industry sectors such as automotive, consumer products, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, high-tech and aerospace. Descriptive statistics, correlation and hierarchical regression analysis were used. The study found that the intensity of supply chain integration directly led to improved business performance.

2. Cheng et al (2004) with the study: "Experimental study on supply chain performance in transport logistics", with the aim to evaluate three areas of transport logistics, seaway, and air freight. and third-party logistics services. A cross-sectional survey (questionnaire) was conducted by 924 companies in the transport logistics industry in Hong Kong. The tests for mean, standard deviation, Cronbach's alpha, reliability, validity, and ANOVA were applied. The results show that there are significant differences in supply chain performance between companies in the three areas.

3. Saeed et al. (2005) "Examining the impact of internal organizational systems on process efficiency and sourcing leverage in the buyer-supplier sector", aims to find understand the connections between inter-organizational systems, buyer-supplier relationships, and production performance. The research method is based on survey to collect data. Research shows that external integration improves the operational efficiency of manufacturing companies.

4. Peterson (2005) argues that supplier integration into new product development: coordination of product, process and supply chain design, aims to examine the role of supplier involvement) level in new product development Data was collected by questionnaire Multiple regression analysis was applied to find the relationship between research factors It was found that supplier involvement has a positive impact on new product development and also produces significant improvements in financial performance.

5. Kim's study (2006): "Effect of supply chain integration on the link between enterprise competitiveness and supply chain performance", designed to determine the relationship interaction between supply chain performance and enterprise competitiveness. Data were collected through a questionnaire of 623 respondents (from Korea and Japan). Confirmatory factor analysis and regression analysis were performed. The study found that supply chain integration influences have a positive impact on operational efficiency.

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6. Devaraj et al. (2007) with the study: "Impact of e-business technology on operational performance: The role of production information integration in the supply chain", designed to determine the impact of information technology on performance. The questionnaire is used as a tool to collect data from different industries. The total number of samples is 1464 from various industries such as computer components, printed circuit boards, electronic equipment and supplies, vehicle bodies and parts. Descriptive statistics and correlation tests were applied to analyze the results. It is found that information technology also supports supplier integration. In addition, it has also been found that vendor integration has a positive impact on performance.

7. Zelbst et al. (2009) study titled: "Impact of supply chain linkage on operational efficiency", to examine the impact of supply chain linkage on operational efficiency. A total of 145 manufacturing and service sector managers were surveyed. The measurement scales are evaluated for reliability and validity and are evaluated. The research hypotheses were tested using multiple regression. Research shows that power-benefit and risk-reduction linkages have a positive and significant impact on performance. Power is identified as the key link for manufacturers and risk reduction is most important in the service sector.

8. Forslund and Jonsson, (2009) study titled: "Obstacles to Supply Chain Integration of the Performance Management Process Between Buyers and Suppliers: Buyer's Perspectives", which explains the supplier relationship constraints and operational tool obstacles that impede supply chain integration. The study is based on a survey of 257 purchasing managers in nine manufacturing industries in Sweden. The mean, standard deviation, and reliability of the scale were applied. The study found that supplier relationship obstacles (lack of trust, different goals and priorities, and lack of parallel communication structures) significantly hindered process integration performance management.

9. Study by Al-Shaar (2010) titled: "Impact of supply chain integration through supply chain response on operational performance in large and medium industrial companies in Jordan: Fieldwork", which explores the impact of supply chain integration on intermediaries (supply chain response) performance. The study used questionnaires, 141 questionnaires were collected. Structural equation modeling is used to test hypotheses and research models. It found that supply chain integration (internal, strategic and external integration) positively affects operational performance.

10. Gimenez, (2011) study titled: "Supply Chain Integration and Performance: Regulatory Impact of Complexity in Supply Chains", aimed to investigate the effectiveness of supply chain integration in different contexts. A survey-based study design was developed to measure various aspects of supply chain integration and supply chain complexity. Data is collected from manufacturers in the Netherlands and Spain from different industries such as Pulp production, chemical production, radio and television, medical instrument manufacturing, vehicle manufacturing motor and machine and computer manufacturing, 145 questionnaires were collected (80 from the Netherlands and 65 from Spain). Factor analysis and regression analysis were performed. The study found that supply chain integration increases performance if supply complexity is high, while a very limited or no degree of influence of supply chain integration can be detected in the case of low sourcing complexity. The results also indicate that in a highly complex supply environment, the use of structured communications to achieve supply chain integration has a negative effect on cost performance.

11. Research by Huo (2012) titled: "Impact of supply chain integration on corporate performance: perspective on organizational capacity", aims to examine the impact of three types of integration. supply chain integration (internal, supplier, and customer integration) for the three types of corporate performance from the perspective of organizational capabilities (supplier-oriented performance, efficiency customer-oriented operations and financial performance). Data was collected from 617 companies in China. Reliability, validity and structural equation modeling methods were performed. Research finds that internal integration improves external integration, and internal and external integration directly and indirectly enhances company performance.

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12. Hamad study (2013) titled: "Impact of supply chain integration on organizational performance and the role of environmental instability: An empirical study of food industry companies in Jordan", aimed to investigate the impact of supply chain integration on the performance of food industry companies in Jordan. The usual descriptive analysis method is used. Questionnaire from 326 respondents for all food industry businesses. Mean tests, standard deviation, t-test, simple regression and path analysis were applied. It has been found that there is a significant impact of supply chain integration on an organization's performance in an environment of uncertainty.

13. Parast and Spillan, (2013) study titled: "Logistics and Supply Chain Process Integration as a Source of Competitive Advantage: Empirical Analysis", aimed at investigating the effectiveness of supply chain integration and logistics on the competitiveness of enterprises in manufacturing enterprises. Structural equation modeling was used to determine the influence of two sets of logistics and supply chain integration practices on competitiveness. 782 questionnaires were collected from the US and 361 usable questionnaires were collected from China. Comparisons of Mean, Standard Deviation and Reliability Factor were performed. The results indicate that supply chain integration is the driving force for operational efficiency. Furthermore, the findings suggest that logistics/supply chain process integration is the most important predictor of a company's competitive position.

14. Han et al. (2013) study titled: "Impact of supply chain integration on firm performance in pork processing industry in China", to investigate the impact of integration supply chain for business operations in the pork supply chain in China. This was followed by a causal study and a survey method to collect data from 229 pork processing facilities. Research suggests that internal integration and supplier relationship coordination are significantly associated with firm performance in both relationships. Information technology integration is not significantly involved in both upstream and downstream relationships. Integrated logistics contributes significantly to the performance of pork processors in relation to downstream customers.

15. Xu et al (2014) study titled: "Relationship between organizational resources, supply chain integration and business performance" in China, to explore the impact of resources within the organization, to inter-organizational capabilities and business performance. 17 questionnaires were used to analyze the composite reliability, AVE, mean variance and Cronbach's alpha test. The results show that top management support and information technology are two important factors driving supply chain integration and these two factors have different roles in improving supply chain integration. In addition, supplier integration has a significant impact on business performance.

From the review of the above studies, it shows that studying the relationship between supply chain integration and performance has been interested by many researchers. However, studies are often carried out in countries with developed economies but are still limited in developing economies like Vietnam, especially in the context of the fisheries sector limited. Therefore, this study investigates the impact of supply chain integration on the performance of seafood enterprises in Vietnam.

3. Theoretical framework and proposed research model

3.1. Supply chain and supply chain integration

A supply chain is considered as a system consisting of groups of activities, processes and sub-processes such as procurement, operations, transportation, and warehousing. It aims to provide products and/or services to consumers or customers that begin with the purchase of raw materials and equipment, then convert it into semi-finished products that will be reprocessed to make products.

Supply chain management is concerned with planning and managing the flow of materials, products, and services between and between these processes. The ultimate goal of supply chain management is to deliver

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products on agreed delivery time, consistent quality and competitive prices to customers, and that is reflected in customer satisfaction and overall organizational performance.

The concept of a supply chain has evolved over time. Chopra and Meindal (2007) state that the supply chain includes all parties involved directly or indirectly in satisfying customer needs, it includes all functions related to the receipt and fulfillment of customer needs. fulfill customer requirements. These functions come from manufacturers and suppliers, warehouses, carriers, retailers, and end customers. Chopra and Meindal (2007) add that the goal of every supply chain is to maximize the overall value created. Wheelen and Hunger (2012) argue that Supply Chain Management is the formation of networks for sourcing raw materials, manufacturing products or creating services, storing and distributing goods, and delivering to customers. Supply chains are used first to reduce costs, then to improve customer service and bring new products to market faster than others between different companies producing the same product or service to satisfy customers.

In a nutshell, supply chain management includes all activities performed by organizations in cooperation with suppliers and customers to satisfy customer needs, requirements and preferences.

Due to intense global competition, organizations create cooperative and mutually beneficial relationships among supply chain partners (Wisner and Tan, 2000). Westbrook and Frohlich (2001), have shown that organizations or companies need to implement supply chain integration to meet the new challenges of the global competitive environment. Many studies propose different definitions of supply chain integration. Pagell (2004), and Han & Omta (2007) have defined supply chain integration as a collaborative process in which companies work together in a cooperative manner to arrive at mutually acceptable outcomes. Zhao et al (2008) described supply chain integration as the extent to which an organization strategically cooperates with its supply chain partners to manage internal processes to achieve goals efficiently flow products, services, information and decisions with the ultimate goal of providing maximum value to customers. Krajewski et al. (2013) defined supply chain integration as the effective coordination of supply chain processes through information flow from the bottom to the top of the supply chain. Supply chain integration can be defined as the process through which all parties involved in the supply chain; Suppliers, organizations and customers, are working independently and interdependently to achieve unified goals such as providing maximum customer value, reducing overall costs. Bagachi et al (2005), Fabee-Costes and Jahre, (2007) argue that supply chain integration is the key to the success of businesses in the global supply chain.

In this study, supply chain integration is defined as the collaborative process between supply chain actors to manage inter-organizational and internal activities to achieve the flow of products, services, and information. Effective communication to deliver maximum value to customers in the right place at the right price and at high speed. Supply chain integration is measured by: supplier, internal and customer integration.

3.2. Supply chain integration elements

According to Chopra and Meindl (2007) supply chain management can be classified into three stages to better understand supply chain integration:

First: Customer Relationship Management: all processes and activities that focus on downstream interactions between the organization and its customers.

Second: Internal supply chain management: all processes and activities focus on internal activities within the organization.

Third: Supplier relationship management: processes that focus on upstream interactions between the organization and its suppliers.

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When starting out, organizations focus on what they can do to manage the business and achieve their goals, as demonstrated by profitability and customer satisfaction, so the main focus is on management. Manage internal processes across departments to achieve efficiency. Then the concept of organizational performance goes hand-in-hand with supply chain performance, so organizations that plan to continue, compete, survive, and outperform others begin to adopt the concept and try to expand the scope of relationship management with other parties in the supply chain (suppliers and customers).

Even effective supply chain management cannot achieve its goals and efficiency unless it maintains internal (between departments) and external coordination and collaboration, hence the importance of Supply chain integration has emerged between business processes and operations. In addition, the supply chain must be designed in a way that ensures all processes, activities, roles, and stages are aligned to support the supply chain strategy. Basic Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is one of the various software systems used to perform the integration between the three phases. Monk and Wagner (2013) defined ERP as a system that can help a company integrate its operations by acting as a company-wide computing environment that includes the provision of consistent data across all business functions. The evolution of information technology allows ERP to grow and be flexible to accommodate all parties in the supply chain. ERP links different applications into a single application that integrates data and business processes such as integrating the following operational functions: marketing and sales, accounting, human resources, purchasing and logistics.

Many studies and academic articles have been written on supply chain management. Some studies are interested in supply chain integration. Some studies look at supply chain performance, while others discuss the mediating factors that influence supply chain integration or performance, or both. Finally, several studies have addressed both factors together (integration and supply chain performance).

Zhang and Huo (2012) focus on dependency and trust and its impact on external integration (suppliers and customers). Frohlich and Westbrook, (2001) studied the rings of integration (supplier and customer). Van der Vaart and van Donk (2008) analyzed the integration from different perspectives: attitudes, patterns and practices. Zhao et al. (2011) emphasize on internal integration and conclude that internal integration is the source of both customer and supplier integration through customer relationship commitment and relationship commitment with supplier.

Rosenzweig et al. (2002) explored the intensity of supply chain integration in terms of competitiveness and business performance. In addition, they studied the mediating effect of competitiveness between supply chain integration and business performance. Alam et al (2014) studied the mediating impact of logistics integration on supply chain performance. The results show that logistics integration has a very significant direct impact on the performance of the supply chain.

Lockamy and McCormack (2004) explored the link between supply chain operations and planning (resource planning, execution, and delivery) and supply chain performance. Zelbst et al (2009) investigated supply chain performance through the impact of linkages in the supply chain. In addition, they assessed the relationship of linkages to supply chain performance. Vaidya and Hudnurkar (2012) explored many criteria of supply chain performance. These criteria include: cost, customer service, productivity, asset management, quality, time, innovation, flexibility/adaptability, supplier profile, measures marketing methods and the possibility of cooperation. Cirtita et al (2012) explain the structure of the supply chain; Supply chain performance references include: flexibility, cost, delivery reliability, asset management efficiency and responsiveness.

Huo (2012) examined the impact of supply chain integration with integrated supply chain elements (Suppliers, Internal and Customer Integration) on three types of corporate activities (related to supplier, customer related and financial performance). Huo (2012) concludes that internal integration improves external integration, and both direct and indirect integration improve company performance. Xu et al (2014) explored intra-organizational resources (Top Management Support and Information Technology) and inter-organizational

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capabilities (Supplier and Customer Integration) and their influence on competitive advantage (Performance). They found that inter-organizational resources were the key drivers of supply chain integration. In addition, integrating both suppliers and customers has a significant impact on business performance. Zhao et al (2013) investigated the impact of supply chain risk (on-demand delivery and supply delivery risk) on supply chain integration (supplier integration, internal and customers) and company performance (achievement of schedule, competitive performance and customer satisfaction).

From above, it clearly shows the importance of relationships between and between supply chain activities, processes, and people performing specific tasks to add value to supply chain partners. overall response. Building on previous studies on the importance of all factors in the supply chain, this study aims to investigate all variables of supply chain integration: Supplier, internal and positive variables customer case.

Vendor integration

Suppliers are the primary and sole source of inputs needed for an organization's operations, so they have an essential role to play in continuing to produce products and services to meet customer requirements row. In the modern era, giant manufacturing organizations tend to build close relationships and partnerships with their suppliers to manage fluctuations in customer demand and reduce cycle times delivery period and time. Today, many suppliers are more involved in the design of products and operations to facilitate manufacturing and meet customer needs.

Stank et al. (2001), define supplier integration as the degree to which a company can cooperate with its major supplier members. Some authors use the term downstream integration to represent vendor integration. Scannell et al. (2000) focused on the analysis of supplier integration. Flynn et al. (2010), also comment on supplier integration as it relates to core competencies in coordinating with key suppliers.

Accordingly, current research has defined supplier integration as a collaborative process between a supplier and an organization to facilitate the sharing of information, knowledge, documents, and experiences. It is measured in specific categories that reflect the nature of relationships, partnerships and other related issues between suppliers and Vietnamese seafood enterprises.

Internal integration

Internal integration is central to the focus of both suppliers and customers, and it is seen as the foundation that maintains stability and continuity for all parties in the supply chain, so the organization cannot integrate suppliers and customers without internal integration. Building the right supply chain strategy relies heavily on having all departments have a common mission, vision, and goals for the organization. Prior to that consensus, each department was looking at two types of customers. The first customer is the primary customer to which the organization plans to provide the final product or service, and the second is the department or employee where other outputs are dependent to further achieve the mission of the organization. them and thus achieve the overall goals of the organization.

Flynn et al. (2010) define internal integration as the degree to which a manufacturer establishes strategies, practices, and process management in a collaborative, synchronous manner to meet customer requirements. and interact effectively with suppliers. Zhao et al. (2011) argue that internal integration emphasizes organizational structure and procedures so it must have cooperation and synchronization to meet customer requirements.

In this study, internal integration is defined as the process of maintaining cooperation and collaboration between functions and departments in an organization to achieve the strategic goals of the organization. It is measured by a set of scales that define the nature of relationships, coordination, and collaboration across organizational departments.

Customer integration

Customers are the lifeblood of organizations. Customer needs and requirements are always changing, so what was considered essential in the past may change in the near future. Therefore, organizations need to monitor the external environment such as political, economic, social, technological and legal changes. Furthermore, the organization must always take the initiative to outperform its competitors in satisfying customer needs.

Customer relationship management is considered an important element in the supply chain. Flynn et al. (2010) argue that customer integration involves core competencies that come from collaboration with key customers. Van der Vaart and Van Donk (2008) analyzed supply chain integration from different perspectives: attitudes, patterns and practices. Rosenzweig et al. (2002) considered supply chain integration as a unidirectional construct, while Zhao et al (2011) considered a broader view for supply chain integration as internal integration. and external integration. Huo et al. (2012) state that both supplier integration and customer integration can be classified as external integration.

In the present study, customer integration is defined as the process of building and maintaining strong relationships and partnerships with customers. It includes sharing knowledge, experience, products, services and recommendations with customers. It is measured by selected items that explore relationships and partnerships and related issues.

The current study deals with supply chain integration including supplier integration, internal integration and customer integration.

3.3. Performance

The concept of performance has emerged from the supply chain strategy, which derives from the overall business strategy. Competitive strategy is defined as the set of customer needs that it seeks to satisfy through its products and services (Chopra and Meindal, 2007). Each organization adopts different competitive strategies, then the organization seeks to provide the right capabilities and resources to achieve the business strategy.

Any company that wants to succeed must align its supply chain strategy with its competitive strategy.

Frohlich and Westbrook (2001) state that eliminating non-value-added activities, reducing order variance, and increasing product flow rate will affect organizational performance. Hult et al. (2002) mentioned that information technology and process innovation can contribute significantly to operational performance. Shah (2009) argues that organizations must recognize the nature of the trade-off between customer service and cost. Organizations strive to gain competitive advantage by aligning supply chain decisions and processes with their business strategy. Shah (2009) argues that supply chain strategy must ensure that the supply chain effectively delivers superior value to the end user. Zelbst et al. (2009) emphasize that the success of the organization is highly dependent on the success of the supply chain in which the organization participates as a partner. Wheelen and Hunger (2012) reviewed Porter's competitive strategies (lower cost, focus on differentiation) and argued that business strategy focuses on improving the competitive position of the business unit. businesses, products and services in a particular industry or market segment. Wheelen and Hunger (2012) show that supplier network resources have a significant impact on firm performance. Alam et al (2014) concluded that logistic integration has a mediating impact on operational performance.

This study considers performance as a group of standards adopted and used by organizations to achieve competitive advantage, customer satisfaction and maximum profitability. In this study, performance was measured using the following aspects: Flexibility, Time (Speed), Quality and Cost as they were considered the most common aspects that were surveyed among the studies. previously saved.

Flexibility

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Building an agile competitive strategy requires commitment to certain actions and activities, among them educating employees about different tasks, motivating employees to work schedules flexibility, teamwork, and increased communication within the organization.

Rosenzweig et al. (2002) define flexibility as the ability of a company to develop flexible operations in a hyper-competitive environment in response to frequent changes in volumes, product mixes, and schedules. The researcher defined flexibility as the ability of an organization to adapt to fluctuations in demand in terms of product or service specification, volume, and on-time delivery. It is measured in specific items that reflect the ability of organizations to weather these fluctuations in demand. Flexibility is a very important factor in the supply chain, the ability to respond to changes in the business environment, is considered a dynamic source of business capacity.

Time (Speed)

Developing a strategy to reduce the time between customer needs until they are met requires the following: forecasting demand systems, coordinating workflows, changing layouts Organize and manage transportation.

To measure performance is expressed by delivery time and lead time. Various studies have determined the duration, lead time and cycle time. Cycle time is the amount of time from completion of one job or task to another, i.e. from starting a process or task to restarting that process or task. Delivery time is the time required from when a customer places an order to deliver a product or service (company and supplier) including production, transportation, processing, warehousing and delivery of the product or service. service to the end customer. Gimenez et al (2011) defined delivery time as the time required to deliver products to key buyers. The researcher adopts the delivery time required by the company to deliver the product or service to the customer according to the agreed timetable. This time is measured by selected items that reflect the speed at which products and services are delivered to customers.

Quality

Developing a strategy based on the quality of products, services and processes requires matching the following: educating employees with specific tasks, applying monitoring systems, motivating employees commitment to quality standards and monitoring of complaints.

The extent to which supply chain activities and processes seek to meet customer needs, requirements and requirements by following ISO rules and standards. From the customer's point of view, the organization should provide reliable service. Juran and Godfery (1998) defined quality as product features that meet customer needs and thus provide customer satisfaction. In this study, quality was defined as the degree to which supply chain integration meets customer needs.

Cost

Formulate a strategy based on reducing the overall costs that lead to out-of-stock as follows: reduce inventory, maximize resource utilization, work-in-process inventory turnover, and eliminate unnecessary activities valuable.

Possibly the most common and important metric for evaluating supply chain performance is cost. Bowersox et al. (2009) define cost as the total cost incurred to perform a particular activity. The organization tries to reduce prices and maximize profits. Vaidya and Hudnurkar (2012) argue that cost is defined as the sum of all costs including: incoming and outgoing freight, warehousing costs, third-party storage costs, handling costs orders, direct labor, administrative and service costs. Cirtita et al. (2012) define cost as the total cost associated with running the supply chain. In this study, the author has defined cost as the total cost incurred when completing all specific activities in the supply chain.

4. Proposing research model

In previous studies, it has been shown that there is a strong relationship between supply chain integration and performance. Some studies have suggested that there is a close relationship between supplier-customer integration and organizational performance, other studies have commented on the presence of a relationship between upstream and downstream interactions. downstream and operational performance, another team ensures the certainty of supplier, internal, and customer relationships that integrate with the overall performance of the organization.

Almost all studies conclude that supply chain integration is considered an important process that affects operational performance. Scannell et al. (2000) conclude that supply chain integration is positively associated with aggregate measures of cost and flexibility. Frohlich and Westbrook (2001); and Vickery et al. (2003) found a positive and direct relationship between information technology integration and supply chain integration. Bagchi et al. (2005) state that supply chain integration affects operational performance and the extent to which integration affects cost and efficiency. Flynn et al. (2010) point out that external integration emphasizes the importance of cooperation and collaboration with suppliers and customers.

Zhao et al. (2011) argue that supplier integration and customer integration play different roles in performance improvement and capacity development. Flynn et al. (2010) found that internal integration and customer integration are more closely related to performance improvement than supplier integration. Gimenez et al (2011) found that integration has a positive effect on performance in terms of profitability, delivery speed, and shipping costs. Alam et al (2014) mentioned that thanks to supply chain integration, suppliers get closer to their customers and can invite customers to orient and manufacture products or services that meet their needs customer's need.

The present study considered supplier integration, internal integration, and customer integration as independent variables, while operational performance factors (cost, quality, time and flexibility) is the dependent variable. More specifically, the aim of the present study was to investigate the impact of supply chain integration on operational efficiency at seafood enterprises in Vietnam.

The proposed research model is as follows:

Figure 1. Proposed research model

5. Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic, which has lasted for the whole year of 2020 with many new strains, has disrupted global seafood trade, changed the trend of consuming seafood products, and strongly impacted import seafood. Creates a lot of instability in production, processing and export in most of the major seafood suppliers in the world.

In 2020, the Covid-19 epidemic caused a decrease in the world's ability to cultivate shrimp and white fish species. It is estimated that the world's aquaculture production in 2020 will reach 82.5 million tons, down 0.6% compared to 2019, accounting for 46.6% of the total world seafood production.

In 2020, regulations to limit fishing quotas to ensure sustainability will continue to be applied in most fishing grounds and be imposed and controlled more tightly. More and more fishing grounds comply with this regulation. Meanwhile, the EU's IUU regulations are also closely monitored, making global fishery production more sustainable and difficult to increase.

The world's catch of fishery production in 2020 will reach 94.5 million tons, down 0.53% compared to 2019, accounting for 53.4% of the total global fishery production. Captured seafood is less affected by the Covid-19 epidemic. The world's total fishery production in 2020 is estimated at 177 million tons, down 0.56% compared to 2019. It is forecasted that the global seafood production this year will be 177 million tons, which will reach 177 million tons in 2021, no increase compared to 2020. In which, capture fisheries will decrease and aquaculture products will increase.

The complicated developments of the Covid-19 epidemic with new strains are making the world's seafood supply unstable in places that are capable of supplying large aquaculture seafood to the world such as India and Vietnam.

Therefore, the solution to integrate the supply chain in the seafood industry is an effective solution to reduce risks caused by natural disasters and epidemics to the economy in general and the seafood industry in particular.

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